

ROLE, SIGNIFICANCE AND HISTORICAL STAGES OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE IN MEDICINE

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ABSTRACT: This article provides information on the importance and role of the science of Latin language and medical terminology in world medicine. In addition, the stage of historical development of the Latin language, its impact on world languages and its place are discussed.

KEY WORDS: latin language, historical period, experience, treatment, medical terminology, pathological conditions

The language of healers originated in the countries of the Ancient East several thousand years ago. The Latin language (self-name - Lingua latina) had a special influence on the development of medical terminology. This language was most developed in the period of Antiquity. Latin was spoken and written by the ancient Romans.

Many years have passed since this historical period, but, nevertheless, it is Latin that continues to be the basic language of doctors today.

Initially, Latin did not act as a "dead" language. It became such only in the 9th century. It was during this historical period that the colloquial form of Latin ceased to enjoy its previous popularity among the local population. People in everyday communication began to switch to new, at that time, languages - such as Italian, French, Spanish, Romanian, etc. Over time, Latin began to disappear from the spoken language of people.

Many people still continue to use words from Latin, as well as phrases from this language. The main reason for this is the unique national character inherent in this language. For this reason, in the names of diseases, pathological conditions, methods of treating and examining a patient, diagnostics and treatments, almost all national sublanguages of clinical medicine use Latin terminology, which can be known as part of any modern "living" language, for example, such terms as arthritis (arthritis), gastritis (gastritis), anemia (anemia), etc.

Previously and now there are several "dead languages". According to the data reflected in the Internet encyclopedia "Wikipedia", a "dead language" can be

represented as a language that does not exist in real living use and is often presented only in the form of written sources, or which is used to a limited extent.

Sometimes dead languages, having ceased to be a way for real live communication, exist only in writing and are used for various purposes in such areas as culture, science, religion.

Perhaps the most popular and in demand in certain areas of professional activity and in certain states is now the “dead” language of Latin.

Now there is no people who would speak Latin.

One of the main reasons why this language can be called one of the most enduring "dead" languages is that Latin is the only active, albeit underused (not colloquial) language today.

In Latin, now, in accordance with the formed Western theological tradition, scientists carry out dissertation research and participate in scientific disputes.

Apparently, there is no other professional activity where the human experience that has developed over the centuries has had such an effective influence on the terminology used in medicine, since one of the disciplines that play a significant role in the training of specialists in the field of pharmaceuticals and medicine is Latin. Doctors have to deal with this language every day when studying medical literature, reading the names of diseases, drugs, reflected in the International Nomenclature for the Names of Chemical Compounds and, first of all, in the formulation.

It is known that mastering a profession occurs in the process of consistent knowledge of the language used in the profession, including a set of special concepts and terms expressing them.

In order for a person to be successful in professional activities in his field, he must have a certain terminology. Mastering Latin in the process of studying at a medical institute pursues a purely professional goal - to prepare a terminologically competent physician.

The terminology used in modern medicine is one of the most extensive and complex systems of terms in terms of conceptual understanding. In this system, there is a huge number of words and combinations of words.

Latin plays an important role in pharmaceutical activity. Almost all newly created drugs are usually translated into Latin. This will allow you to easily navigate in a huge number of existing drugs.

Thanks to scientific progress, the Latin language will be a very relevant and in-demand language in the medical field for a long time to come.

Currently, the language of doctors is used internationally as a scientific language in a whole set of medical and biological disciplines around the world. In this regard, it is very obvious that any doctor, as well as a pharmacist, should know the principles underlying the construction of Latin word formation, as well as the main Latin terms used in medicine.

At various historical times, attempts were repeatedly made to transfer to national medical concepts within the framework of such languages as German, English, French. But, despite this, the position of Latin remained unshakable, thanks to which Latin continues to be considered the language of doctors today.

In this regard, despite the fact that Latin is usually called a "dead" language, for physicians this language is alive and widely used in professional activities.

This circumstance acts as a unifying factor in training in medical and pharmacological specialties around the world.

Also very important is the description of those features that are inherent in Latin, thanks to which this language can be called a unique way of communication between doctors of different historical eras around the world:

- capacity and conciseness. This feature lies in the fact that one Latin word is able to convey the amount of information that in other languages can be conveyed only with the help of several words or phrases;
- the presence of a linguistic structure, according to which such parts of Latin words as a prefix, root, suffix, are able to retain the same meaning in different words;
- Latin medical terminology has a complex structure, but it is easy to understand, provided that you have knowledge about the individual elements of this structure;
- systematic, due to which, as a result of the presence of a large number of prefixes and suffixes, it is possible to describe and classify diseases;
- versatility. From year to year, for many years, medical students around the world learn Latin and apply the acquired knowledge in their practical activities.

In order for students to successfully master the medical language, which is Latin, students should have an initial educational base. A physician with a classical education received in any state can easily understand medical prescriptions made by doctors in another country, since the names of medicines, as well as anatomical names, are Latin. So, all organs and parts of the human body, drugs are named in Latin terms or have Latinized names.

Who has not come across recipes that were written in an incomprehensible, cryptic language? Latin is like a symbol of some kind of dedication, involvement in something

that is unknown to other people. Prescriptions are written in Latin according to rules that are understandable to pharmacists anywhere in the world.

The terminological training of future doctors should include not only an understanding of Latin terminology, but also practical skills for its active use in activities.

I would also like to emphasize that Latin is simply beautiful. Knowledge of Latin has its own specifics for doctors. After completing a Latin language course at a medical school, a student is unlikely to be able to talk to other people and make complex sentences and long speeches from the point of view of construction. However, as a result of studying this discipline, the student should develop an understanding of anatomical terms, diagnoses of diseases, as well as the ability to write prescriptions in Latin.

Mastering Latin terms, among other things, will allow you to quickly get used to understanding other medical disciplines. At the same time, in itself, the Latin language used to be and now remains one of the most important academic disciplines in teaching a doctor.

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